

Empowering Farmers as Entrepreneurs; Consideration of Indian Farms as MSME's for Viksit Bharat 2047 Making Farms as A MSME Units for A Goal of India Becoming Fully Developed Nation

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Abstract:

India's journey toward Viksit Bharat 2047 cannot be achieved without transforming the lives-livelihoods of its own farmers. Traditionally viewed as primary producers, farmers are largely remained dependent on fluctuating markets, limited value addition which lead them to uncertain/ variable incomes. This paper argues for a requirement of shift and repositioning Indian farms as Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and farmers as entrepreneurs rather than mere cultivators. By integrating Indian agricultural farms within the MSME framework, farmers can gain improved access to credit, technology, better formal markets, skill development, global market and government incentives. Entrepreneurial farming encourages value addition, diversification in agriculture, agri-processing, branding, and participation in national and global supply chains. Such a transition not only enhances income stability but also promotes rural industrialization, employment opportunities, and inclusive economic growth. The study examines policy possibilities, institutional support systems, and structural reforms necessary to enable this transformation. Empowering farmers as entrepreneurs is not merely an economic strategy; it is a social and developmental emerging necessity that aligns agriculture with India's broader vision of sustainability, global competitiveness as well as self-reliance. Recognizing farms as MSMEs can serve as a powerful agent in building a fully developed rural economy and achieving the vision of a developed India by 2047.

Keywords: Viksit Bharat 2047, Agricultural Entrepreneurship, MSME Integration, Agri- MSMEs, Rural Development, Farmer Empowerment, Inclusive Growth, Agro- Processing, Financial Inclusion, Sustainable Agriculture

Introduction:

The year 2047 marked for 100 years of independence, as India progresses towards the goal of Viksit Bharat 2047, is not only a celebration of the past [3], but also a vision for the future. This is to make a developed India that is inclusive, more equal, highly resilient and greatly responsible. But industries or technology cannot make a nation developed. True development must be inclusive for every segment of society, especially those who make up the foundation of our economy. In India,

that foundation is agriculture — and at its heart lie the farmer [2].

For many years, Indian farmers are known mainly as the people who grow our food — the fruits, rice, wheat, and all vegetables that reach our homes every day. They wake up before sunrise, work long hours in the fields, and expect the unexpected seasons to be kind. Because of them, our country has food in the plates and rural families have some source of income.

But behind this very important role, there is a difficult reality. Large number of

farmers are not earning enough to live comfortably and complete their basic needs. Most of them own only small land, which limits productivity and sell. The prices of crops keep changing, and farmers often have to sell their produce at low rates because they have no choice. At the same time, the cost of transportation, urea fertilizers and labor need for farms, keeps increasing. If the rains fail, come too late, or if floods destroy the crops, a whole season's hard work can disappear in a few days which leads farmers into debt trap. [6].

Many farmers also do not have proper storage facilities, so they have to sell their crops quickly, even when prices are very low. Farmers cannot wait for better rates because the produce they grows may spoil. Getting loans from banks is other obstacle as getting loans not easy task for everyone. The banks lending rules, documentations, and delays in payment transfer make it difficult, so many farmers borrow money from private lenders which are at high interest rates. In very short time, this leads to heavy debt on farmers. Because of all these challenges, farming always faced a daily struggle to live. Even farmers work from morning till night, many of them are only able to manage their basic needs which is often not guaranteed. Saving money, improving their living conditions, or planning for the future becomes impossible in such situations.

If India truly wants to achieve the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047, we need to rethink how we see and consider our agriculture [3]. Farming should not be looked at as just a traditional activity done to survive. It should be seen as a real business with opportunities to grow and earn better income. In today's world, income does not come only from growing crops. It also comes from processing food, packaging food, marketing, and making a brand, exporting. We can even sell it through digital

platforms. Agriculture holds potential to become a strong agri-business sector if farmers receive the right guidance, support and recognition.

Among many one practical way is to bring the change and treat Indian farms as Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The MSME sector already plays a big role in India's economy by increasing exports, increasing employment and contributing to GDP growth- 32% [1]. If farms are also recognized as MSMEs, farmers can get easier access to Schemes, bank loans, better technology, training, and good access to markets [4]. This can help them go beyond selling raw crops. They can start small food processing units, focus on value addition, create their own brands, and even run small agri-based businesses. Selling of this end products can make them financially stable

Seeing farmers as entrepreneurs can also bring social change. Rural youth may start seeing farming as a good and profitable career instead of moving to cities for work. Women can take part through self-help groups and small agri-business activities [7]. New businesses in villages can create local jobs and reduce migration to cities [10]. Most importantly, farmers can gain confidence and independence. They can take their own business decisions and feel important of being active contributors to the country's growth.

The idea of connecting agriculture with the MSME system also supports other national goals like financial inclusion, digital growth, self-reliance, resilient and sustainable development. This entrepreneurial farming can encourage new ideas such as organic farming, climate-friendly agricultural practices and agro-technology. This approach can reduce dependence on imports and will lead to

improve India's position in global agricultural markets.

This paper want to highlights the idea of empowering farmers by recognizing their farms as MSMEs. It explains how this approach can lead to raise in farmers' incomes, strengthen rural areas which ultimately will support India's economic growth. By making farms as enterprise units, the country can unlock the unleashed strength of its agriculture sector and build a stronger rural economy.

On the way to Viksit Bharat 2047, empowering farmers is not just about improving agriculture but it is about changing the future of the nation through agriculture. When farmers are treated as entrepreneurs and farms will be considered as enterprises unit then rural India can move beyond survival and step toward steady and long lasting growth, by becoming a strong pillar of a developed India.

Background And Literature Review:

India has always been seen as a farming country. Even today, many families depend on agriculture for their daily income. Farming feeds the nation and also provides work to people in villages. It plays an important role in keeping the economy stable. But even with all this importance, agriculture has faced many problems for years. Most farmers own small and divided pieces of land, which limits how much they can grow. The cost of fuel, seeds, fertilizers and labor keep increasing. Weather has become more uncertain due to climate change and irrigation is not available everywhere. The market prices also keep changing. Because of these, farming has become a risky activity with high investment and low returns for many farmers [11].

Over the years, the government has launched many schemes to increase production of farms and support farmers. While these steps

have helped in some ways, simply growing more crops has not always meant higher income for farmers. So this schemes alone are insufficient. For many years the Economic Surveys of India pointing out that weak conditions to bargain, poor access to markets, and low income still affect farmers' financial condition [11]. This shows that increasing production alone is not enough. Because of this, researchers, leaders and policymakers have started thinking about new ways to improve the situation instead of depending only on traditional farming methods.

At the same time, the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector has become one of the strongest wing of India's economy. MSMEs contribute is large in share to GDP, exports, and employment in both rural and urban areas [12]. Studies show that when small businesses receive proper loans, training, and infrastructure support, they can grow into stable and successful enterprises. This leads to an important thought: if MSMEs can boost growth in manufacturing and services sector, why we cannot apply similar business approach to agriculture? In recent years, many discussions are focusing on agricultural entrepreneurship. Research on Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) and agri-startups shows that farmers can earn more when they do not just sell raw crops but also take part in processing, manufacturing, packaging, branding, and direct selling [13]. This approach helps farmers increase their income and become active participants in supply chains and export markets. These findings suggest that agriculture can work like a business enterprise and not just as a basic primary production units.

The vision of Viksit Bharat 2047 also highlights the need for growth that includes everyone and remains sustainable. Policy documents talk about balanced financial

inclusion, rural industrial growth, and regional development [14]. Since agriculture supports a large part of the rural population, improving this sector is necessary to reach national development goals. If farms are recognized as MSMEs, farmers could receive businessman status. This may help them access bank loans more easily, benefit from government schemes, technical support, and connect to organized global markets.

Although many studies discuss agricultural problems and MSME growth separately, very few directly link the two by formally suggesting that farms should be treated as MSMEs under the Viksit Bharat 2047 framework. Most research looks at improving farm productivity or strengthening MSMEs on their own. The idea of combining both sectors into one development strategy has not been studied in depth.

Therefore, this study builds on earlier research and policy ideas to examine whether recognizing Indian farms as MSMEs can be a practical and meaningful solution. By bringing together agricultural reform and enterprise development, India can move toward stronger rural prosperity, better employment opportunities, and more stable economic growth. In the context of Viksit Bharat 2047, supporting farmers as entrepreneurs is not just about economics; it is also about fairness, dignity, justice and building a sustainable future for the nation.

Objectives Of Studies:

The main aim of the study of this topic is to understand how farmers can grow not just crops, but also as entrepreneurs, and how this can help India move toward the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047. Agriculture still plays a very important role in the country, especially in villages where many families solely depend on

farming for their daily income and survival [15]. Even with such importance, farming has mostly remained limited to growing and selling crops, without being fully connected to mainstream business systems. The view in this paper tries to explore whether considering Indian farms as Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) can open new paths for future economic growth and rural development in India.

One of the major objective of this research is also to study the current social and economic condition of Indian farmers and potential. Many farmers struggle with low income, large dependency on middlemen, challenges in getting loans, lack of proper storage infrastructure, transport, and market facilities in concerned with agriculture [16]. With understanding these types of real-life problems of farmers, the study wants to discuss whether the present system can prevents farmers from working as independent economic decision-makers. We must understand that it is important to look at these challenges before suggesting that farms can be treated as MSMEs.

Another key objective of this paper is to study the MSME sector and its contribution to India's economic and social development. MSMEs are known for creating employment/ jobs, increasing- diversifying production, and supporting exports [17]. Economics study teaches us that, when small businesses receives good financial support, training, and infrastructure development, they often grow steadily, surely and become strong contributors to the economy. This study want to examine whether as kind of model can work for agriculture. It want to study whether bringing farms under the MSME can boost agricultural household income through framework can improve access to bank loans, government

schemes, formal market systems etc. The research also focuses on the idea of agricultural entrepreneurship. Instead of only growing crops, farmers can also take part in activities like food processing, exports, packaging, branding, and direct selling. Studies show us that such diversification and agri-based enterprises can increase rural incomes in a meaningful way [18]. This objective looks at simple and practical ways farmers can adopt business thinking in their work and how policies can support them during this shift.

In addition, the study aims to understand how recognizing farms as MSMEs can support larger national goals such as inclusive growth, rural industrial development, self-reliance, and sustainable progress under Viksit Bharat 2047. Agriculture supports a large rural population (65% Indian Population lives in rural area)[6], so improving this sector can reduce poverty, create job opportunities within villages which will lead to reduce migration to cities, and ensure balanced regional development.

Another important objective is to study what could be the possible challenges in bringing Indian farms under the MSME category. Farming is definitely different from factories or service businesses. It largely depends on natural conditions like weather, and natural conditions, rain, seasons. Because of these differences the practical difficulties may arise. This study want to carefully discuss these possible issues so that realistic as well as workable approach can be suggested.

Finally, the research aims to offer practical and real policy suggestions for strengthening farmers as entrepreneurs. These includes better access to affordable loans, support for agri-startups, stronger Farmer Producer Organizations (FPO), use of digital platforms for the sell of agricultural produce,

and awareness programs about enterprise like farming. The focus is on simple and workable suggestions that can lead to a real difference in Indian economy through agricultural prosperity.

So, this study is not only about policies, initiatives and economic model. It is also about people living in rural India. Empowering every farmer as entrepreneur means giving them respect they deserve, confidence they required, and financial independence. By exploring the idea of treating farms as MSMEs, this research hopes to add meaningfully to the discussion on inclusive and sustainable growth for achieving Viksit Bharat 2047

Research Questions:

- a. Can Indian farms be integrate in the structural and practical sense into the MSME framework without affecting their agricultural identity?
- b. What are the major economic and institutional challenges that prevent farmers from operating as entrepreneurs in the current system?
- c. How can recognizing farms as MSMEs improve farmers' access to credit, government schemes, and formal financial systems?
- d. To what extent can entrepreneurial farming contribute to increasing rural income and reducing economic vulnerability?
- e. How can agricultural entrepreneurship promote value addition, processing, branding, and direct market participation among farmers?
- f. What role can Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) and agri-startups play in supporting farms as MSMEs?
- g. What policy reforms are required to legally and operationally recognize farms under

the MSME classification system?

- h. How can empowering farmers as entrepreneurs contribute to inclusive growth and rural industrialization under the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047?
- i. Will the integration of agriculture into the MSME ecosystem help reduce rural-urban migration and create local employment opportunities?
- j. Is recognizing farms as MSMEs a sustainable and practical long-term strategy for achieving economic resilience and self-reliance in India?

Research Methodology:

This study uses a descriptive and analytical research to understand the idea of empowering farmers as entrepreneurs by recognizing their farms as Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The focus of the topic is more on policies, structure, and required reforms rather than just field experiments. Because of this, the research is mainly based on secondary data instead of primary surveys.

The information I used in this study is taken from government information sources like NITI Aayog reports, Economic Survey, Budget document and discussion in parliament. These sources were studied because they provide us information, updated data, policies, and discussion which is important and directly connected us to the objectives of this paper which we are considering.

With the target to understand the relationship between agriculture and the MSME sector at a structural level, comparative study is also conducted. The study of existing reports, documents, policies, and published data is conducted. This method helps in understanding bigger picture like financial inclusion, rural employment growth, and

entrepreneurship development, industrialization in rural and inclusive growth under the big vision of Viksit Bharat 2047.

An analysis method is also used in this study. It compares the structure of Indian agriculture with the features of MSMEs sector in India. This comparison looks at factors such as, types of activities, capital investment needed, employment opportunities and regulations. By studying the differences and similarities, the research tries to find whether bringing farms under MSME classification is next agriculture revolution or not.

Along with this, the study connects three main areas to each other that is, national development goals of India, current challenges faced by our farmers and benefits available to MSME sector in India. By linking these three areas together, the paper can build a good argument in support of consideration of farms as business enterprises.

The more focus of this research is on policy and analysis of agriculture structural within India. By using authentic and reliable official sources, the research tries to make the meaningful analysis.

Overall, the methods are considered carefully to examine whether empowering farmers as entrepreneurs through MSME recognition can really go work or not. The main goal is to find if this idea can support long term and effective growth of Indian agriculture sector which will help India to move closer to the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047.

Consideration Of Farms As Msme's For "Viksit Bharat 2047":

A. Current Status of Indian Agriculture:

In India agriculture still plays an important role in Indian economy. In Indian villages, many families are largely depend on

farming either directly or in some indirect way for their daily living and basic needs [19]. Even though agriculture gives employment to a large number of rural people, the share of agriculture in the country's GDP is low as compare to manufacturing and service sector. This clearly shows us that many farmers are earning less considering their hard work and time they invest. Low agriculture productivity and farmers low income continue to be a serious issue. Most of Indian farmers own small land, which make difficult the use of modern technique [20]. Another big problem Indian agriculture sector faces is unstable and variable

income from farming. Farmers depend heavily on the rain, and if the rainy season are early or late or insufficient, the entire crop produces suffers. Above that, market prices always keep fluctuating, and many farmers sell the produce through middlemen, most often at lower rates/prices [19]. All these multiple problems make it clear that traditional farming methods solely are not enough for long-term agricultural and rural economic stability. Because of this, it is necessary to think for new approaches that can help to improve profits and reduce the risks Indian farmer's faces.

TABLE 1: CURRENT STATUS OF INDIAN AGRICULTURE:

Indicator	Current Scenario in India	Importance for Study
Share in Employment	Around 42– 45% of workforce dependent on agriculture [19]	Shows agriculture supports large population
Share in GDP	Around 15– 18% contribution to GDP [19]	Indicates income-productivity gap
Average Landholding Size	Approx. 1.08 hectares (small & fragmented) [20]	Limits economies of scale
Dependence on Monsoon	High in many regions	Creates income instability
Access to Institutional Credit	Improving but still uneven [22]	Financial inclusion remains partial

This table shows that agriculture employs many people and their income levels is low so, new structural reform is needed. Overview of MSME Sector in India

The MSME in India are considered as one of the strongest pillars of India's economic development. They contributes largely in employment, exports, and manufacturing output [21]. MSMEs are often considered as the backbone of the Indian economy because they create great job opportunities at relatively lower investment compared with the large scale industries.

Government initiatives helps MSMEs by providing them easier credit accessibility, by

enabling digital registration systems, and all other various incentive schemes like PLI's [21]. These enterprises are getting benefited from well-designed financial systems, and policy support. If similar structural supports are extended to agriculture, farmers and villages may also enjoy access to organized economic opportunities. This comparison between agriculture and MSMEs can creates a strong foundation for consideration of farms as MSMEs.

TABLE 2: FEATURES OF MSME SECTOR IN INDIA

Indicator	MSME Sector Status	Relevance to Farmers
Contribution to GDP	Around 30% of GDP [21]	Shows economic strength
Share in Exports	Approx. 45–48% of total exports [21]	High global competitiveness
Employment Generation	Over 11 crore jobs [21]	Strong job creation capacity
Government Support	Formal registration (Udyam), easy credit schemes	Can benefit farmers if included
Access to Finance	Priority sector lending, Mudra loans	Reduces dependency on informal lenders

This table explains that how support by government makes MSMEs economically strong .

B. Why Farms Should Be Considered as MSMEs:

Agriculture and enterprise since traditionally, have been treated as separate sectors from other. Whereas, when we closely examine farming activities, they also involve production, investment, distribution, management, risk, and market participation. This qualities are very similar to those of small enterprises and MSMEs.

By recognizing farms as MSMEs, farmers can have access to credit, insurance, government subsidies, and other

developmental programs [22]. MSME registration, also improves transparency and financial inclusion. This could reduce farmer's dependency on moneylenders and can improve long-term sustainable and economic development.

Further, treating agriculture farms as enterprises/MSMEs can encourage diversification in food processing, branding, and packaging of produce. Instead of selling raw produce, farmers can create value-added products, which can increase their income and strengthen rural economy.

TABLE 3: COMPARISON – TRADITIONAL FARMING VS. MSME MODEL

Basis of Comparison	Traditional Farming	MSME- Based Farming Model
Nature of Activity	Subsistence- oriented	Business- oriented
Market Approach	Sell raw produce	Value addition, branding, processing
Financial Access	Informal & limited	Institutional credit access
Risk Management	Highly vulnerable	Insurance & structured support

comparison shows that recognizing farms as MSMEs can shift agriculture from struggle to growth.

C. Economic Benefits for Viksit Bharat 2047:

Considering farms as MSMEs can play an important role in India's long-term economic development. It will be key to make India fully developed by 2047. First, it will industrialized rural area by encouraging small scale agro-processing units and other kind of

village-level enterprises [23]. When such activities will grow in rural India, they can create job opportunities close to home for local population. This can help in reducing migration to cities, because now people may find work in their own villages.

Second, it can improve India's export.

Many of our agricultural products are in demand foreign countries. However, due to lack of branding, standard, processing, and good packaging, we often do not able to compete in the global market. If we make our farming in a more business-oriented way, product quality can improve and packaging can meet global standards. This can make Indian agricultural produce more competitive in international markets [23].

Third is, enterprise-based agriculture supports the idea of self-reliance. A large amount of produce is wasted after harvest because of poor storage infrastructure. If we link farms with processing and small industries, these losses can be reduced and more profit can be earned in agriculture. This approach is closely linked with the broader goal of sustainable economic growth under Viksit Bharat 2047.

TABLE 4: POTENTIAL ECONOMIC IMPACT OF RECOGNIZING FARMS AS MSMEs

Area of Impact	Expected Outcome	Link to Viksit Bharat 2047
Rural Employment	Increase through agro-processing units	Reduces rural- urban migration
Farmer Income	Higher due to value addition	Supports inclusive growth
Export Potential	Improved packaging & branding	Enhances global competitiveness
Women Participation	Growth in SHG-led enterprises	Promotes gender equality
Youth Engagement	Agriculture seen as entrepreneurship	Encourages innovation

table links this idea with other national development goals.

D. What is the Social Impact of Empowering Farmers as Entrepreneurs:

The transfer of in farming and farms into enterprises and entrepreneurs respectively is not just about money and economy, it is also about social change. Farmers will get more capability and freedom to take decisions related to pricing, marketing, and production. This provision can improve their respect and also give them better financial independence. This will be beneficial to India's aspiration to be fully developed by 2047

Entrepreneurial farming can also lead to change, in rural youth's view about the agriculture. Many young people leave villages because they think that farming does not give enough income. But if agriculture is treated like a proper business, with profit and future expansion opportunities, youth may start

seeing it as a serious and rewarding career option [24]. In the same way, women can take active part in agri-based MSMEs through self-help groups and cooperative models. This not only increases family income but also supports gender inclusion and strengthens the whole community.

In addition, when rural enterprises will grow stronger, villages also begin to develop better facilities by their own. Local infrastructure like cold storages, small processing units and roads in rural areas can be improve. Farmers can use digital platforms for selling and payments. It can also encourage new ideas such as climate-resilient farming, which is very important in today's changing Indian weather conditions and considering unpredictable seasons.

E. Challenges in Implementation:

Though the idea of recognizing farms as MSMEs looks impressive, there are several challenges it might face to make this idea successful. One major issue is legal. Agriculture and manufacturing units does not fall under the same category of rules and regulations, so there is a scope of confusion [20]. Clear and simple policy guidelines from government are necessary, otherwise farmers have to face more complications instead of benefits. So simple and clear regulations are required.

Another big challenge can be awareness. Many small farmers may not fully understand what MSME registration means or how to manage an enterprise. The process of registration, maintaining records, and handling formal procedures can feel complicated for them. So, proper training and capacity-building

programs will be very important for smooth implementation of this initiative [22]. Without guidance and support, the idea may remain only on paper and later will be in dust.

Infrastructure is also one serious concern. In many rural areas, storage facilities are limited or poor, cold chains are weak, and transport networks are not sufficiently developed. If these basic facilities are missing, it will be difficult for farms to grow as enterprises. Even if they get MSME status, practical growth may slow down because of these structural gaps.

Still, despite these difficulties, the idea is not impossible. With the careful policy reforms, proper planning, and strong will, this transformation can be done. It may take efforts and time, but it remains highly relevant for India's long-term development journey

TABLE 5: MAJOR CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTATION

Challenge	Description	Possible Solution
Legal Classification	Agriculture & MSME governed separately	Policy reform & clear guidelines
Awareness Gap	Farmers unaware of MSME benefits	Training & extension programs
Infrastructure	Lack of cold storage & logistics	Rural infrastructure investment
Digital Literacy	Limited adoption in rural areas	Digital training initiatives

Recommendations For Policy Change:

After looking at the present condition of Indian agriculture and also considering the strengths of the MSME sector, I personally feel that empowering farmers as entrepreneurs needs clear, careful and practical policy support. It is not enough to simply say that farms should be treated as MSMEs. There must be a proper system that makes this changes smartly, fair, and helpful especially for small and marginal farmers.

First of all, there should be a clear legal

provision that allows suitable farms to register under a special category, maybe something like "Agri-MSMEs." This separate category can prevent confusion between factories and farm-based enterprises. While making such rules, the government must ensure that small farmers are not left out because of strict turnover or investment limits. The conditions should match rural realities and not be too complicated. Once farmers get formal recognition, they can access bank credit, insurance, subsidies, and digital platforms like Udyam. This can slowly improve their

economic position.

Secondly, access to affordable credit is very important in this. Even now, many farmers depend on informal money lenders, which often leads to heavy debt. Banks and financial institutions should design simple loan procedures for farm enterprises. Repayment schedules should match crop cycles, so that farmers are not forced to repay before harvest. Interest support and working capital for agro-processing and value addition can help farmers earn more. At the same time, financial literacy programs must be organized in villages, so that farmers can learn basic business skills like budgeting, and simple investment planning.

Another strong recommendation is skill development and entrepreneurship training for farmers. If farmers are expected to work like entrepreneurs, they must learn about marketing, branding, packaging, digital selling, and even export rules. Agricultural colleges, Krishi Vigyan Kendras (KVKs), and MSME development centers can work together to provide such training. Special focus should be given to rural youth and women farmers, because they have great energy and ideas. Proper training can slowly change the mindset from survival farming to the growth-based thinking.

Infrastructure development is also very necessary. Without good storage systems, cold chains facilities, proper transport, and continuous electricity, it will be difficult for farm enterprises to expand. The government should link agri- MSME plans with rural infrastructure schemes. Public-private partnerships can also help in building storage units and logistics systems in villages. Better infrastructure will reduce post- harvest losses and improve overall profit. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) can also help in this.

In addition, agro-processing and value

addition at the village level should be strongly encouraged. Instead of selling raw crops at the low prices, farmers can process and package their produce by their own to earn more. Capital subsidies, tax benefits, and technical support can help set up small food processing units. Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) and cluster-based models should also be strengthened. When farmers work together, they can reduce risks and increase their bargaining power in the market.

Digital, road- rail connectivity and better market linkages are equally important. Farmers should be trained to use online platforms, digital payment systems, and government-supported portals like e- NAM. Selling directly to consumers can reduce dependence on middlemen and increase transparency and profit. Real-time market price information can also help farmers take better decisions.

Finally, coordination between ministries is very important. The Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of MSME must work together to design joint schemes for this. Awareness programs at village level must be conducted so that farmers actually understand and use these benefits. Policies should not remain only in official documents, they must reach the ground.

In my view, empowering farmers as entrepreneurs is not just an economic reform, it is also a social change. It is emerging necessity of viksit Bharat 2047. With proper finance, infrastructure, and policy support from government, farms can slowly grow into strong rural enterprises for future. This change can increase income, reduce migration, and strengthen inclusive growth. If implemented in a careful and inclusive manner, these measures can play a significant role in achieving the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047 and make rural India more confident and prosperous.

Future Research Required:

Even though this study has discussed the idea of empowering farmers as entrepreneurs by treating Indian farms as MSMEs, I personally feel that there is still a lot of scope for more research in this area.

First is, future researchers can conduct on ground surveys. This will give us information about farmer's readiness for this. It is important to understand what farmers think about recognized their farms as MSMEs. What they think about activities such as branding, marketing and digital platform? Understanding their need, daily requirement and expectations can help in designing policies.

Secondly, more research can be done on basis regional requirement and differences. Agriculture in India is very diverse, and farming conditions are also diverse in every state. For example one initiative may work in a well-irrigated area may not work in a rain dependent agriculture area.

Another important area for future research can be financial study after the initiative. Future researchers can create set are rules to calculate the development in rural area. They can study profit, loan given and change in per capita income.

Future studies can also focus on the role of technology in agri-MSMEs growth. For example, they can study how digital platforms, artificial intelligence, and agri-tech start-ups can support farmers. The impact of digital literacy in villages is also an important to study.

There is also a need to study further the social impact of this transformation on agriculture. Researchers can examine how it impact employment, women's participation, health, youth participation, and migration. It is important to study whether is transformation makes the rural area prosperous.

Environmental sustainability must be studied in this light. Future study must check whether this new agro-MSMEs are conducting their activities in ecofriendly manner. It is important to note this initiative does not disturb the local environment.

In the end, researchers can use case studies from foreign countries where agriculture is closely connected to MSMEs. Case studies from other region can give us new ideas and reduces the possibilities of failure

There is large future scope in this topic. But one need to understand that we cannot see our dream of developed nation without considering potential of agro-MSMEs/Farm-MSMEs .In conclusion, while this paper provides an understanding and need of empowering farmers as entrepreneurs to make India fully developed by 2047.

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